

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 1.6 to AD4.1 – Information leaflet for Legal Guardians

WP 4

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

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Project approved by *[specify name of the committee]* with ref. n° XXXXX

PARC_GS_Information leaflet for Legal Guardians

Information Leaflet for Legal Guardians

[title of study, e.g. PARC biomonitoring study on

exposure to [specify name of pollutant(s) or type of study [aligned study on ...]]

[A personalized introductory message follows, which aims to make the information relevant to your audience in order to get their attention and interest to read on, while being accurate and not overpromising

Let's create a healthier future together, by preventing exposures to harmful chemicals /

Let's improve our health by preventing exposures to harmful chemicals]

Information for study participants

Your child is invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide whether or not your child and you wish to take part, please read the following information to understand why the research is being done and what it involves. We are happy to answer any questions or concerns you may have. The participation is voluntary and your child and you may opt out at any time without disclosing your reasons.

European Partnership for the Risk Assessment of Chemicals (PARC)

PARC is a 7-year project under Horizon Europe – a framework programme of the EU for funding research and innovation. PARC is funded by the European Commission and national governments and includes experts from 28 countries and EU agencies. It started in 2022 and will run until 2029. The overall goal of PARC is to develop a next-generation chemical risk assessment in order to protect human health and the environment.

PARC and its importance to you and to public health

We are all exposed to a complex mixture of chemicals on a daily basis. Some chemicals may harm health and for this reason they must be regulated in the environment, consumer products, food and drinking water and in certain workplaces. PARC aims to understand human exposure to such chemicals and the

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related health risk by using **human biomonitoring** (measurements of environmental chemicals or their reaction products in biological samples collected from people).

The results will be used, wherever appropriate, to support policy makers with their decisions regarding the introduction or adaptation of relevant laws and interventions for the safe management of chemicals and the protection of human health in Europe. By engaging with participants like your child, PARC will help to raise awareness among the public and promote actions to prevent exposures to potentially harmful chemicals.

The present study [*specify name of the study*] is carried out the frame of PARC. In [*specify country*], it is under the responsibility of [*specify Program Owner*].

Learn more at [*website of the specific study, if available*] and www.eu-parc.eu.

Why is this study being done and who approved it?

The study has been approved by [*specify national Bioethics Committee*] and complies with the European general data protection requirements.

It is taking place to: [*explain research questions. Some examples are given below.*]

- find out if the current safety and control measures used across Europe can protect the public from the exposure to chemicals of concern.
- develop new methods to assess the exposure to these chemicals.
- investigate potential associations between exposure to these agents and adverse health events
- identify good practices and propose relevant health intervention or prevention policies
- ... other]

Why your child is asked to take part?

Your child has been selected randomly [*specify how the selection took place, for example: through a population registry*] to represent [*describe the study population in easy to understand terms (what makes a person eligible to participate in the research)*] in [*specify country*].

By agreeing to take part, your child and you can help to ensure that children are properly represented in the survey results. This is important for making the study more reliable and useful.

If recruiting through an intermediary organization (e.g. school, Ministry of Education, workplace): The [*specify the intermediary organization*] has consented to participate in the study and has agreed to allow us to extend an invitation to you to participate.

How will the study be carried out?

The study will take place *[specify time period]* in *[specify your country]* and *[if applicable specify the number other European countries]*. It will include a total of *[specify total number of]* participants and *[specify number of national participants]* of them will come from *[specify your country]*. Each participant will provide **biological samples** (*[specify type]*). The legal guardians will complete a questionnaire about their child and possible sources of exposure. We will analyze this information to assess your child's exposure to *[chemicals of concern. Specify which chemicals will be investigated]*. Biomarkers of exposure and biomarkers of effect will be investigated in biological samples.

[The following section is optional for studies using specific reply cards. Please delete if not needed. Please adapt according your specific reply cards used. Templates for reply cards are not available]

What do you have to do if you agree to take part?

If your child and you agree to participate, please complete and return the enclosed **green** reply card ("I and my child want to participate") within *[specify number]* days from its receipt.

Adjust the following text according to your study plan. The suggested option is to ask those who do not wish to participate in the study to answer a short non-responder questionnaire anonymously by using an ANONYMOUS orange reply card, which includes a non-responder questionnaire (i.e. no GDPR requirements). You may use a different approach, if you find it more appropriate.

The following text supports the suggested option, using an anonymous "orange reply card":

If your child and you do not want to participate, you can help us improve future studies by returning the **orange** reply card within *[specify number]* days from its receipt. By answering a few optional questions completely anonymously, you can help us to understand how the people who choose not to take part in the study compare to the people who want to take part. **Please return the orange card** *[specify how and to who]*. *You may consider using online versions of the reply cards for convenience.*

[The following section is optional for studies using specific reply cards. Please delete if not needed. Please adapt according your specific reply cards used. Templates for reply cards are not available]

What happens after we receive your reply card?

[Adapt the text below according to the needs of your study plan]

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1. On receiving your green “yes” card, we will confirm if your child is eligible to participate in the study. This study will include volunteers that must meet the following requirements: *[specify eligibility criteria]* and we can only include participants that fulfill them, up to a maximum of *[specify number]* individuals.
2. If your child does not fulfill the eligibility requirements or the maximum participation limit of this study has been reached by the time when we received your green card, you will receive a letter about it. You may also be asked whether you wish to be contacted by your national study coordinator for participation in future HBM studies.
3. If your participation is confirmed, we will contact you to agree on a suitable date for your appointment with our research team at *[adapt according to your study plan, e.g. OPTION A: our Examination Centre, [specify location / street address] and your travel costs will be covered by us / OPTION B: your home]*.
4. You will be asked to confirm your willingness to your child participation in the study by completing and signing the enclosed consent form in duplicate. You will keep one copy for your records and we will keep the other for our records. You and your child can ask any questions you wish and you and your child can take the time you need to clarify any concerns prior to signing.
5. Prior to the appointment, you will receive a **reminder (pre-visit) letter/sms/phone call [with notice of any preparations required before the appointment. Specify the required preparations, e.g. provide morning urine]**. You can indicate your preferred way to receive this reminder on your reply card.

How do your child and you have to prepare for the visit?

No special preparation is necessary. *[If any preparation is required, specify it here (e.g. able to provide morning urine), since it may affect the person’s final decision whether to participate in the study].*

What will happen during our appointment?

[Adapt the text as appropriate for your study, e.g. Option A: On arrival at the Examination Centre a member of our team will be available to answer any questions you may have / Option B: A member of our research team will visit you at home]. Your child and you will have time to ask any questions you may have and receive answers.

If you have not already completed and signed a consent form prior to the appointment, you must do so at this point.

The researcher will take the samples from your child *[specify type biological samples]*.

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Urine: Your child is asked to give a urine sample in the plastic container provided. If support by you is necessary, please help your child. The urine sample has to be the first morning void. The sample collection is done by your child at your toilet at home. You receive detailed written instructions for the correct collection of the sample. *In addition, you receive a sampling questionnaire.*

Hair: *[Insert easy-to-understand text describing the hair sampling in detail]*

We will ask you to complete a questionnaire to collect information about your child, his/her living conditions, food intake, and his/her possible contact with chemicals.

The visit will last no longer than *[specify number]* minutes. *Include if applicable, e.g. if the appointment takes place in an examination center: You will be given a fixed payment to cover your travel expenses.* Include information how the questionnaire has to be completed, in with time frame, etc. In case you use an online questionnaire.

What will happen to your child's samples, data and results?

[The Principal Investigator of the study must ensure compliance with all European/national legal and ethical requirements. Adapt the template as necessary].

Your child's samples and your child's and your data will be used only according to your informed consent and in a way that protects your privacy according to the European regulations GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) and EUDPR (Regulation (EU) 2018/1725) and national requirements. The released results of the study will not identify you in any way.

Your child's and your personal data, your child's and your data collected with the questionnaire and the results of the analysis of your child's sample will be stored pseudonymized. This means that a code will be used to remove your child's and your personal identifiable information to protect your child's and your privacy. Only the study owner can combine the code with your child's and your personal data. All personal data are stored in a secure way at *[specify your institution]*.

Your child's coded samples will be transferred to specialized laboratories for analyses *[specify where the analyses will take place]*. Your child's samples will be examined to measure different substances/biomarkers *[explain which chemical contaminants will be analyzed and why]*. Your child's samples will then be stored at *[specify place and length of storage]* for possible use in future ethically approved studies of chemical exposure. Coded data collected from your child and other participants will be stored and used for research purposes and may be combined with other data from different sources and shared among PARC partners. The sharing of data will be facilitated through dedicated data

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infrastructures and/or Information systems (such as IPCHEM, which is the European Commission Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring, <https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>).

The overall results of the study will be provided to national and European authorities to support policy actions related to chemical management for public health protection and will be published in scientific journals. They will also be disseminated to other stakeholders, including the general public, scientists and other interested parties.

How can you and your child learn about the results of the study?

When the study is completed [*specify according to study plan: in approximately XX weeks/months*], your child and you will be informed by [*specify name of person, e.g. study coordinator*] about your child's personal results [*specify the biomarkers which will be reported to the participant*], unless you expressed a wish not to receive them on your certificate of informed consent.

In the event that high levels of chemicals are detected, you will be advised to review your results with your family / personal doctor/ general practitioner.

You will also be informed about the *collective* results of the study. These will be published as a study report and will be publicly available at [*specify correct website, e.g. official PARC website and/or national study website*].

How will your child's and your privacy be protected?

[It is advised that a written procedure for the protection of personal data is in place at the legal entity carrying out the study and that it is in compliance with the GDPR requirements].

Your child's and your privacy is protected by complying with the requirements of the European **General Data Protection Regulation** [*and specify relevant national legislation, if applicable*]. The [*specify name of legal entity*] is responsible for the protection of your data against loss, unauthorized access /use, modification / disclosure or other misuse. The Data Controller is [*specify (name, function, e.g. study coordinator or Director of legal entity)*].

Our Data Protection Officer is at your child's and your disposal for questions or concerns related to data protection and may be reached at the following contact information: [*specify (name and contact information of the Data Protection Officer of the legal entity)*].

All data processing will be done in such a way, that it is no longer possible to attribute your child's and your data to you without the use of additional information. Your child's and your name will be replaced by a code. Information which identifies your child or you (name, contact details) will be kept separately and under protective measures. All electronic and paper records will be protected from unauthorized

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access of your child's and your private information. Published reports of the study will not contain information that can be traced back to your child and you. Third parties will not have access to your child's and your personal results, unless you consent to.

For the present study *[specify name]* as the responsible party collects and processes your child's and your data. In general, a differentiation must be made between: 1) those personal data by which a person can be directly identified (e.g. name, date of birth, address), 2) pseudonymised personal data, e.g. data for which all information that allows direct conclusions to be drawn about the specific person is either removed or replaced by a code and made unrecognisable. However, despite compliance with these measures, it cannot be completely ruled out that re-identification is possible.

(3) Anonymised data for which a traceability to the specific person can be ruled out.

In the present study, the following data are proceeded: *[specify, e.g. First name and surname, date of birth, sex, state/district, telephone number, e-mail address, address]* of your child and you.

Information on *[specify, e.g. living environment, living habits, leisure activities, diet, education, occupation, health data (namely: selected diseases, medication, vitamins and supplements, dental status)]*.

The use and evaluation of your sample(s) (analysis results) constitutes the processing of special personal data within the meaning of Article 9 (1) of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This is health data in the broader sense. This processing is therefore only lawful with your express consent.

Handling of personal data: Only the person responsible for the present study and his/her deputy have access to the data by which you are directly identifiable (see (1)). They are subject to a general confidentiality obligation and the strict provisions of data protection law.

Use of the data: *[specify study owner]* stores the personal data used to identify you (see (1) - for example, if your child and/or you wish to opt out and need to be assigned to it with regard to the deletion of the data and the destruction of the sample(s) - under special technical security precautions. The remaining data are stored pseudonymously (see (2)) and are also stored under special security precautions. In the course of studies, which are carried out on the basis of your sample(s), the data is only processed and used anonymised. It is not possible to draw any conclusions about your child and you. Only anonymised data will be used for any publications of study results and no individual data will be passed on.

Storage period, destruction/deletion: The collected samples are stored for *[specify]* years at *[specify]*.

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The data collected by means of questionnaires and the analytical measurement results are stored pseudonymised (see (2)). The code that enables the pseudonymised data to be assigned to your person is only stored at *[specify]* in a technically and organisationally secure manner.

Should you (wish to) opt out, your personal data will be deleted and your sample material destroyed immediately.

Your consent forms the legal basis (Art 6 para 1 lit a GDPR) for the processing of your child's and your personal data. Your child and/or you can revoke your consent to the collection and processing of your data at any time without giving reasons. After your revocation, no further data will be processed.

Data subject rights: According to the GDPR, your child and you are generally entitled to the rights of information, correction, deletion, restriction of processing, data portability and objection, as this does not render the objectives of the present study impossible or seriously impair them and as this is not conflict with other legal provisions.

Your child and you have the right to complain to the *[specify country]* data protection authority about the handling of your data.

Data protection officer: If your child and/or you have any questions about the handling of your child's and your data, please contact the data protection officer at *[specify]* in the first instance.

Why do we need your written consent?

Your written consent confirms that you agree as legal guardian of your child that your child will voluntarily take part in the study after understanding what is required from you and your child and what your and your child's rights are. Your child and you have the right to withdraw your participation without any consequence at any point (including any data or samples already provided, if they have not been completely anonymized and so impossible to be traced back to your child, and if the samples are still not analysed) and the right to choose if you want to receive your individual results or not. You will also confirm that we can contact you in the future to tell you about your child's personal results or for historical, statistical or scientific purposes. A copy of the Certificate of Informed Consent, which you will be asked to complete and sign before your child is taking part in the study, is attached to this leaflet and you can keep it for future reference.

How will your child and you benefit if your child participates?

- Your child and you will have the right to receive your child's personal results (if you wish) *[by law any new high incidence of chemical levels should be reported]*

- Your child and you will receive information regarding your exposure to specific chemicals and, wherever applicable, the associated potential health impact.
- *[Describe any other incentives, if applicable]*
- Your child, you and all citizens in *[specify country]* and in Europe will benefit from the collective results of the study, which will be used to *[adapt as appropriate, e.g. understand the exposures of people to harmful chemicals and how these can affect the human body / develop harmonized or new methods to measure exposures / develop better chemical management policies across Europe]*.

Are there any risks if your child joins the PARC study?

Some children may experience minor discomfort during the collection of urine or hair samples. Hair samples are taken by trained staff. Urine samples are taken by your child himself/herself. If necessary we ask you to support your child when taking the urine sample. *[If applicable: Study participants will be covered by insurance for any adverse events relevant to their participation, without any charge to them]*.

Are there any costs to you?

No, the study will be conducted at no cost to you. Participation is voluntary, without reimbursement. *[If applicable: Travel and out of pocket expenses can be claimed back through [specify reimbursement procedure]*.

What if your child and/or you have any concerns or complaints while your child is taking part in the study?

Your child's and your wellbeing are our foremost priority, and we will take all necessary precautions to ensure your child's and your comfort and safety. If your child and/or you have any concerns during your appointment, please discuss them with our research team or at any time by contacting the study leader *[Title, Name, Tel No., Email address]*. Your child and you have the right to opt out of the study for any reason (without the need to disclose this). In the unlikely event that your child and/or you want to file a complaint about the study, you may do so by contacting *[Title, Name, Tel No., Email address]*, who is not formally connected to the study and serves as an independent overseer of its implementation.

What happens if your child and you say yes, but your child and/or you change my mind later?

Your child and you are free to withdraw from the study, without any consequences by *[sending an e-mail to / calling specify the name, and email and/or phone number of the responsible person]*. We will ask you to confirm your child's and your wishes by signing the attached withdrawal form. On this form you can indicate one of the following options:

- “No further contact but my child's samples and data can be used”.

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We will no longer contact you, but have your permission to retain and use information and samples that you have already provided.

- “No further contact and my child’s samples and data cannot be used”.

We will no longer contact you and will destroy your child’s samples and your child’s and your data, unless they have been completely anonymized and we cannot trace them back to your child and you. For the integrity of the study and in the interest of public health, we will retain your child’s coded data in analyses that have already been completed. We will retain your signed consent and withdrawal forms as a record of your wishes and for audit purposes.

Your child and you can request a copy of these forms from us using the contact details provided below.

Who do you contact if you have any questions or would like further information about the study?

You can contact [\[title, name, function, phone number, email\]](#) or visit the websites [\[website of the specific study\]](#) and www.eu-parc.eu.

Thank you for reading this leaflet and for considering to join the PARC study!

Visit our website to find out more! www.eu-parc.eu

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